

Muon Background Simulation for SABRE South at SUPL

Guangyong Fu

ARC Centre of Excellence for Dark Matter Particle Physics, Australia
School of Physics, The University of Melbourne, Melbourne, VIC 3010, Australia
On behalf of the SABRE South collaboration

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Abstract

The SABRE (Sodium-iodide with Active Background REjection) South Experiment will directly search for a dark matter annual modulation signature with ultra-high purity sodium-iodide crystals. Neutrons produced by cosmogenic muons can mimic the dark matter-nucleus recoil signal, and they also show an annual modulation signature, therefore the muons and related background distribution needs to be carefully studied. The SABRE South detector will be operated at Stawell Physics Underground laboratory (SUPL). The muon and muon-induced background can be greatly suppressed by the 1025 m-thick rock overburden. The construction of SUPL finished recently and a muon telescope with $8\ 300 \times 40 \times 5$ cm plastic scintillator detectors will be commissioned at SUPL for muon background measurements. This paper will present the results of simulations of muons at SUPL with CRY and Geant4. Distributions of surface muons from different generators are compared. And a preliminary result of muon modulation amplitude at SUPL is calculated with MUTE.

1 Introduction

Since Fritz Zwicky predicted the existence of dark matter when studying the Coma Cluster of the galaxies in 1933 [1], numerous pieces of evidence from cosmological observations have been accumulated. DAMA/LIBRA observed a dark matter-like annual modulation signal at Gran Sasso National Laboratory (LNGS), Italy [2], but it has not been confirmed or rejected by other similar experiments.

The SABRE (Sodium-iodide with Active Background REjection) South experiment will search for dark matter annual modulation signals reported by DAMA/LIBRA experiment with an array of ultra-pure NaI(Tl) crystals. Details about the detector setup can be found in the SABRE Technical Design Report [3]. Among all the background contributions for SABRE South, cosmogenic muons can generate spallation neutrons that can mimic the annual modulation signals expected from dark matter. This study presents a muon background simulation for SABRE South at SUPL (Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory, Australia).

2 The Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory

The Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory, in the active Stawell Gold Mine, is the first deep underground physics laboratory in the Southern Hemisphere. It is 240 km northwest of Melbourne in Victoria, Australia, as shown in Fig. 1. Under the 1025 m flat overburden of rocks, the muon flux at SUPL is attenuated to a millionth to the surface. The construction of SUPL finished in 2023, and SABRE South commissioning will start soon and is planned to complete in 2024.

Figure 1: Left: SUPL is located in the Stawell Gold Mine, 240 km northwest of Melbourne, Australia. Right: The total muon flux at various underground laboratories as a function of vertical overburden depth. The blue points are under a mountain overburden while the others under a flat overburden. The parameterisation is taken from Ref. [4], a scale factor is added to fit the sites with a mountain overburden.

3 Muon distribution

Muons are mainly produced in the upper atmosphere of Earth from the decay of pions and kaons generated by primary cosmic rays interacting with atmospheric nuclei. Muons and related backgrounds present a similar annual modulation signature, and muon induced neutrons can mimic the dark matter nuclear recoil signal in the crystal detectors. Therefore muon and related background distribution at SUPL need to be carefully studied.

3.1 Muon distribution on surface

To simulate the underground distributions, muons need to be generated at sea level. As shown in Fig. 2, the energy distribution of sea level muons are calculated with the Gaisser model, the Gaisser/Guan model [5], MCEq [6], and CRY (Cosmic-Ray Shower Generator) [7] and compared with measurements [8, 9]. The original Gaisser model does not take into consideration the earth's curvature and therefore overestimates the low energy muon flux. The distributions from other generators show good consistency with experimental data. Here we will use CRY to generate muons at sea level.

Figure 2: Energy distribution of surface muons calculated by different generators and compared with experimental data at 0° (left) and 75° (right).

3.2 Muon distribution at SUPL

The underground muon distribution at SUPL is simulated with Geant4 (release 4.11.02) with surface muons generated by CRY. A threshold of 100 GeV is used to process only high energy muons to save simulation time. Those muons then pass through 1025 m of rock with a density of 2.8 g/cm^3 . The Geant4 packages EmStandardPhysics, EmExtraPhysics and DecayPhysics have been used for the transport of muons through the rock. The simulated result for SUPL is shown in Fig. 3 and compared with results for SUPL and other similar underground laboratories calculated from the empirical model [4].

Figure 3: Left: Angular distribution of underground muons. Right: Energy distribution of underground muons. The curves are calculated with empirical model [4] for underground laboratories (the values on the legend show the depth of the lab in km.w.e.). The red points are from simulation based on CRY and Geant4. All the results are normalised for comparison.

3.3 Muon modulation

The annual change of temperature and pressure in the upper atmosphere results in a change of interaction rate of mesons with the atmospheric nuclei, therefore the muon flux also presents an annual modulation. The relative modulation amplitude of muon flux as a function of effective temperature and pressure can be expressed as:

$$\frac{I_\mu - \langle I_\mu \rangle}{\langle I_\mu \rangle} = \alpha \frac{T_{\text{eff}} - \langle T_{\text{eff}} \rangle}{T_{\text{eff}}} + \beta(P - \langle P \rangle), \quad (1)$$

A summary of dark matter, muon and muon-induced neutron modulation is presented in Table 1. Although the phase of dark matter modulation is about one month ahead of muon and related background in the Northern Hemisphere, Ref. [10] points out that adding a modulated neutrino component can shift the combined signal phase forward. As the muon phase in the Southern Hemisphere is opposite to that in the Northern Hemisphere, the unique location of SABRE South is able to disentangle the muon contributions from dark matter in synergy with SABRE North at LNGS, Italy. For SUPL, which is located under a flat overburden of 2.87 km.w.e, a preliminary calculation of the muon modulation amplitude by MUTE [11] gives a result of 0.79%, and the phase is around January.

Table 1: Modulation of dark matter, muon and muon-induced neutrons.

Modulation	Experiment	Mean rate	Amplitude	Phase
Dark matter (2-6 keV)	COSINE [12]	-	0.0092(67) dru	127.2 ± 45.9 d
	ANAIS [13]	-	0.0003(37) dru	152.5 d (fixed)
	DAMA [2]	-	0.01014(74) dru	142.4 ± 4.2 d
Muon	COSINE-100 [14]	3.795 ± 0.003 _{stat.} ± 0.110 _{syst.} × 10 ⁻³ /m ² /s	0.60(20)%	179 ± 19 d
	MINOS [15]	1.65(12) × 10 ⁻³ /m ² /s	2.66%	203 ± 36.2 d
	DM-ICE17 [16]	2.93(4) /crystal/d	12.3(17)%	22 ± 9 d
	LVD2011 [17]	3.31(3) × 10 ⁻⁴ /m ² /s	1.5%	185 ± 15 d
	OPERA [18]	-	~1.5%	176 ± 4 d
Muon-induced neutron	Borexino [19]	3.432(3) × 10 ⁻⁴ /m ² /s	1.36(4)%	181.7 ± 0.4 d
	LVD2017 [20]	-	0.34(4)%(solar)	~ June 2012 (solar)
	LVD2017 [20]	-	9.3%	7.0 ± 0.4 _{stat} ± 0.5 _{sys} m
	Borexino [19]	-	2.6(4)%	6.0 ± 0.3 m

4 Conclusion

The muon distributions on surface from different generators are compared in this paper. Underground distributions at SUPL is simulated with CRY and Geant4. And a preliminary result for muon modulation at SUPL is calculated by MUTE to be 0.79%. The SABRE South detector will start to be commissioned at SUPL soon and completes in 2024 after the SUPL construction finished recently. A muon telescope consisting of 8 300 × 40 × 5 cm plastic scintillator detectors will be commissioned at SUPL to measure the flux, angular distribution and modulation of muons underground.

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